

while noticeable activity was recorded against *Alternaria brassicae*.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF 2-AMINO-4-PHENYL-5-P-AZOBENZENE SULPHOANAMIDO THIAZOLES

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	R _f
1.	Hydrogen	246-247	85	0.88
2.	Guanidinyl	238-240	90	0.76
3.	Acetyl	202-208	85	0.90
4.	2-(1-Phenyl pyrazolyl)	199-201	80	0.87
5.	3-(5-Methyl isoxazolyl)	201-208	80	0.94
6.	2-Thiazolyl	225-227	90	0.88
7.	2-(5-Methyl 1,3,4-thiadiazolyl)	230-282	85	0.74
8.	4-(2,6-Dimethyl pyrimidyl)	233-235	80	0.94
9.	2-(Pyrimidyl)	228-235	95	0.78
10.	2-(4,6-Dimethyl pyrimidyl)	209-211	80	0.72

All compounds gave consistent nitrogen analysis.

Anticancer activity test was done at Tata Cancer Research Institute, Bombay against mouse tumour system P 388 but all the compounds were found inactive.

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References

1. K. N. GAIND and J. M. KHANNA, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1964, **26**, 34.
2. K. N. GAIND and S. K. GULATI, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1966, **28**, 272.
3. L. S. GOODMAN and A. GILMAN, "The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics", 4th Edn., MacMillan, New York, 1970, p. 1111.
4. E. PROFFT, H. TRUBNER and W. WEUFFEN, *Arch. Exp. Veterinaermed.*, 1967, **21**, 225.
5. O. T. SAVULESCH, V. BARBU and V. TUDOESCU, *Phytopathol. Z.*, 1967, **59**, 129.
6. *Can. Patent*, 820919, 1969; *Chem. Abs.*, 1969, **71**, 124012.
7. S. C. SHARMA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1967, **40**, 2422.
8. N. K. DAS, G. N. MAHAPATRA, and M. K. ROUT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **50**, 32.
9. H. G. GARG and R. A. SHARMA, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1970, **59**, 348.

Constituents of *Rhus punjabensis*

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FAMILY Anacardiaceae which consists of 73 genera and about 600 species is rich for its biflavonoidic constituents. The genus *Rhus*, one of the largest genera of the family, is chiefly distributed in the warm temperature region of both hemispheres extending into the tropical and cold temperature region. An attempt has been made to study the

complex mixture of biflavonoids in the leave extracts of *Rhus punjabensis* (procured from Gopeshwar Hills, Chamoli Distt., India).

The phenolic extractives after preliminary purification and tlc examination on silica gel using benzene-pyridine-acetic acid (36:9:5)¹ developing solvent showed two bands, labelled as RPI and RPII. They were separated by preparative thin layer chromatography.

Although RPI was chromatographically homogeneous, on methylation and tlc examination it was found to be a mixture of three methyl ethers, one major and two minor ones. The major methyl ether labelled as RPIMII was separated by preparative tlc, and characterized as agathisflavone hexamethyl ether, m.p. 162-64°, by spectral analysis and comparison with authentic sample^{2,3}. The two minor methyl ethers, obtained by methylation of RPI, were identified as amentoflavone and robustaflavone hexamethyl ethers by comparison with authentic samples (R_f values, characteristic fluorescence in uv light and co-tlc)^{4,5}.

RPII was identified as hinokiflavone, i.e. 1-5, 11-5, 1-7, 11-7, 11-4' pentahydroxy (1-4'-O-11-8) flavone by its spectral properties as well as those of its methyl ether, m.p. 260-64° and acetate, m.p. 237-40°.

References

1. K. K. CHEXAL, B. K. HANDA and W. RAHMAN, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1970, **48**, 484.
2. A. K. VARSHNEY, W. RAHMAN, M. OKIGAWA and N. KAWANO, *Experientia*, 1973, **29**, 784.
3. A. PELTER, R. WARREN, J. N. USMANI, R. H. RIZVI, M. ILYAS and W. RAHMAN, *Experientia*, 1969, **25**, 351.
4. A. K. VARSHNEY, M. AQUIL, W. RAHMAN, M. OKIGAWA and N. KAWANO, *Phytochemistry*, 1973, **12**, 1501.
5. A. PELTER, R. WARREN, N. HAMEED, N. U. KHAN, M. ILYAS and W. RAHMAN, *Phytochemistry*, 1970, **9**, 1897.
6. M. KAMIL, M. ILYAS, W. RAHMAN, N. HASAKA, M. OKIGAWA and N. KAWANO, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin I*, 1981, 553.

Synthesis and Ion-Exchange Properties of Thermally Stable Stannic Silico Selenite: Separation of Cu²⁺ from Zn²⁺ and Mn²⁺

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SYNTHETIC inorganic ion-exchangers are found to be thermally more stable than their organic counterparts but the search for materials with still greater thermal stability continues. The thermal stability of silica (SiO₂.xH₂O), a naturally occurring weak inorganic ion-exchanger, is very high. Literature reveals that silica has been used in synthesising

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